

ABSTRACT

Academic expectancy stress is an unpleasant psychological situation due to educational expectations from parents, teachers, and the educational system. Honor students are exposed to different stressful events as they pursue their academic journey, making mental toughness one of the most critical components in achieving academic success and subsequently making the psychological qualities of students a determinant of how they can address the demands brought by pressurized situations. This descriptive-comparative and correlational study determine the degree of academic expectancy and mental toughness of senior high school honor students enrolled in a Catholic University in Negros Occidental. Academic Expectancy Stress Inventory and Mental Toughness Questionnaire 18 were used among the 214 senior high school honor students. The findings indicate a high degree of academic expectancy stress among honor students, which signifies a high degree of mental distress concerning some anticipated frustration associated with failure. Furthermore, honor students possess a high degree of mental toughness, which indicate a high degree of mental ability to resist and overcome doubts, worries, concerns, and circumstances that obviate success. Finally, there is a significant relationship between the two constructs considered in this study. Thus, honor students with high academic expectancy stress also possess a high mental toughness.

Keywords: *Social Science, Academic Expectancy Stress, Mental Toughness, descriptive-comparative design, descriptive-correlational design, Philippines.*

INTRODUCTION

Academic expectancy stress is an unpleasant psychological situation due to educational expectations from parents, teachers, peers, and family members, educational systems, examinations, and the burden of homework (Sarita, 2015). Furthermore, high expectations are a general tendency among human beings. Parents expect their children to excel academically to prove their social status. In the same way, teachers also expect high from the students to uphold the institution's name. In this process, the students try to work hard to achieve high results, and if they fail, they experience academic expectancy stress (Subramani & Venkatachalam, 2019). Secondary students face a wide range of ongoing academic-related stressors, which refers to typical daily hassles, such as ongoing academic demands (Pascoe et al., 2019). Students face many academic demands, such as examinations, class participation, monitoring progress in their subjects, and fulfilling teachers' and parents' academic expectations, which induce much pressure among them (Ghosh, 2016). Thus, students need characteristics such as mental toughness to overcome their academic expectancy stress.

Mental toughness is one of the essential psychological concepts which describes one's ability to cope with pressure, stressors, and challenges. In general, mental toughness is an umbrella term that denotes enabling psychological characteristics across a range of achievement contexts that promote mental health (Drinkwater et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2017). Crises, adverse life events, challenges, and stressful situations constitute a substantial facet of human experience and are often inevitable. From the perspective of many individuals, the consequences of adversity negatively affect both physical and mental health and frequently result in impairments in social, educational, and occupational functioning (Price et al., 2002; Scott et al., 2011; Springer et al., 2007). In this context, honor students are exposed to different stressful events as they pursue their academic journey, making mental toughness one of the most critical components in achieving academic success and subsequently making the psychological qualities of students a determinant of how they address the demands brought by pressurized situations (Endozo, 2019).

Studies have shown that academic demands seem more pressing in Asia than other continents because Asian cultures, including Filipino culture, value education. Everyone in the Philippines expects students to do well in academics (Calaguas, 2013). From a general perspective, the academic community has imposed a stringent requirements putting school administrators and teachers under enormous pressure to produce high test scores in the modern education system, resulting in students' experiencing high academic expectancy stress (Ghosh, 2016). Students with high educational attainment in the Philippines are bombarded with many stressors (Arevalo et al., 2018), adding to the high mental distress experienced by honor students. Furthermore, the desire to maintain that honor motivates the students to overcome mental distress caused by academic expectations. The researcher has observed and experienced that senior high school honor students immerse themselves in a rigorous

and demanding academic environment, specifically in a selected Catholic School. They stay up late at night to prepare for their academic requirements. They must attend school early in the morning, do their homework, comply with performance tasks, and participate in extra-curricular activities. In line with the new curriculum, outcome-based education adds to the pressure and academic expectation stress among senior high school honor students. This concept of high academic expectancy stress has been gradually increasing as premised on the philosophical belief that failing to hold the students' high expectations denies them access to high-quality education. However, this issue has been taken lightly (Arevalo et al., 2018) even in the academe.

In the Philippine setting, local studies about mental toughness (Endozo, 2019; Juan & Lopez, 2015; Maghanoy, 2013) involved athletes, athletes playing specific sports, university students, and academic expectancy among college students (Arevalo et al., 2018; Calaguas, 2011, 2013). A study conducted by Perino et al. (2019) explored the coping strategies of senior high school graduating students toward their academic stress. However, there is still a dearth in the literature regarding senior high school honor students as respondents and constructs of academic expectancy and mental toughness, which are the significant concepts of this study.

This study was conducted mainly to assess the degree of academic expectancy stress and mental toughness of senior high school honor students of a Catholic School in Negros Occidental and the relationship between these two constructs. The study findings became the basis for a personality development program that would overcome the academic expectancy stress and strengthen the mental toughness of the senior high school honor students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study utilized a quantitative descriptive-comparative and correlational research design. The descriptive-comparative research was used to measure the difference in the level of academic expectancy according to the students' demographics and the difference in the level of mental toughness according to the senior high school honor students' demographics. Moreover, descriptive-correlational research was used to measure the relationship between academic expectancy stress and mental toughness of senior high school honor students of a Catholic School in Negros Occidental, using standardized tests to extract statistical data appropriately.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents of this study involved 214 out of 479 senior high school honor students enrolled in the Academic Track – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), Accountancy and Business Management (ABM), and Humanities and Social Science (HUMSS) and Technical, Vocational and Livelihood Track – Home Economics Strand of a Catholic School in Negros Occidental for the academic year 2019-2020. The number of respondents was determined using stratified random sampling. After securing the list of senior high school honor students enrolled for the academic year 2019-2020, the sample size was computed using the Raosoft calculator. The fishbowl method was utilized to establish randomization in the selection process.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher wrote a letter to the office of the University President of a Catholic School in Negros Occidental, asking for permission to conduct the study in the senior high school department with their honor students as respondents of the study. After that, a communication letter was sent to the senior high school department's Principal as a sign of courtesy. A letter asking for the list of honor students was addressed to the senior high school academic coordinator of the selected Catholic School to determine the number of prospective respondents. Parental assent was asked from the parents of the identified senior high school honor students, and an orientation about the study's objectives was conducted among the participants. Once all the permits were secured, the researcher scheduled a specific date for the survey's actual administration. The researcher, with the list of honor students as a reference, administered the two questionnaires simultaneously. After gathering the data, the researcher encoded the raw data and sent the files to the statistician for analysis and interpretation.

Data Analysis Procedure. The researcher used the frequency count to determine the respondents' profiles when grouped according to sex, grade level, strand, award classification, and monthly family income. The quantitative data gathered from the conduct of the Academic Expectancy Stress Inventory (AESI) and Mental Toughness Questionnaire 18 (MTQ18) was analyzed to establish a relationship between the two constructs. To ensure that the data set was normally distributed, the Shapiro-Wilk W test was utilized and yielded a score of .059 for AESI and .061 for MTQ18, which is interpreted to be statistically significant. The main problem of the study employed the descriptive analysis, explicitly using the mean to determine the level of academic expectancy and mental toughness

of the respondents when they are taken as a whole and grouped according to the identified variables. For the inferential problems, comparative analysis, specifically with the independent sample t-test, was used to determine the differences in academic expectancy and mental toughness when grouped according to sex and academic honors. At the same time, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the difference in the level of academic expectancy stress and mental toughness when classified according to birth order, strand, and family monthly income. Finally, correlational analysis, specifically with Pearson r , was used to determine the relationship between academic expectancy and mental toughness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents. Table 1 presents the demographics of the senior high school honor students of a Catholic school in Negros Occidental. Regarding sex, most respondents were female, comprising 58%, and male honor students comprised the remaining 42% of the sample size. Gold and silver distinctions constitute 50% of the sample size for academic honors. Regarding the honor students' strands, 69% came from Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) with 148 students, followed by 14% of the Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) with 29 students. Next is 13% from Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) with 28 students. Lastly, 4% came from the Technical, Vocational & Livelihood - Home Economics Strand (TVL-HES), with nine students as respondents of this study. Senior high school honor students who are the youngest of their families make up 39% of the sample size. Next, 31% of the honor students are eldest, followed by middle children, which is 21%, and finally, honor students who are only children comprise the remaining 9%. When grouped according to their monthly family income, 23% of honor students belong to the family group with 40,001 and above as their monthly income, followed by 33% belonging to the family group with 20,001 to 40,000 monthly income, and to complete the group, 44% of honor students belong to a family with 20,000 and below as their monthly family income.

Table 1. Profile of the respondents

Variable	n	%
Sex		
Male	90	42
Female	124	58
Birth Order		
Eldest	67	31
Middle	44	21
Youngest	83	39
Only Child	20	9
Strand		
STEM	148	69
ABM	29	14
HUMSS	28	13
TVL - HES	9	4
Academic Honor		
Gold Distinction	107	50
Silver Distinction	107	50
Family Monthly Income		
Low	94	44
Average	71	33
High	49	23
Total	214	100

Degree of Academic Expectancy Stress. Table 2 presents the degree of academic expectancy stress of senior high school honor students in a Catholic School in Negros Occidental. As a whole ($M=2.81$, $SD=0.61$), the degree of academic expectancy stress of the senior high school honor students is high. This signifies that honor students have a high degree of mental distress concerning some anticipated frustration associated with academic failure. When grouped according to sex, female honor students ($M=2.88$, $SD=0.60$) scored higher than male honor students ($M=2.70$, $SD=0.61$); nevertheless, both sex groups have a high degree of academic expectancy stress. Regardless of their birth order, senior high school honor students have high academic expectancy stress. The eldest scored 2.87 ($SD=0.58$), while the youngest scored 2.76 ($SD=0.62$). When grouped according to academic honor,

results showed a slight difference between the mean scores, where students with silver distinction ($M=2.82$, $SD=0.58$) scored higher than students with gold distinction ($M=2.80$, $SD=0.64$). Concerning the strand, honor students from TVL-HES scored highest ($M=2.95$, $SD=0.44$) among the four strands, with ABM ($M=2.74$, $SD=0.64$) as the lowest. Concerning family monthly income, senior high school honor students with below-average monthly family income scored 2.83 ($SD=0.64$), which is higher than students with high monthly family income ($M=2.75$, $SD=0.56$).

When taken as a whole ($M=2.81$, $SD=0.61$), results showed that senior high school honor students experience a high degree of academic expectancy stress. A high degree of academic expectancy stress is interpreted as a high degree of mental distress experienced by honor students in response to some anticipated frustrations associated with the fear of failing to reach their expectations. These may signify that students generally consider academic expectations from their parents, teachers, peers, family, and themselves as a great source of academic stress, especially for those running for honors in a Catholic School. They are expected to perform better compared to non-academic honor students. The thought of not performing well in academics adversely affects the degree of academic expectancy stress among students (Pariat et al., 2014). They acquire a high degree of academic expectancy stress because of the time they dedicate to their studies, the efforts and resources they exhaust to meet their academic demands, and fear that they might not meet what their parents, teachers, peers, family, and even themselves expect (Feld, 2011). This study is similar to Calaguas's (2013) findings that first-year college students generally have high academic expectancy stress. Likewise, Arevalo et al. (2018) stated that students with high educational attainment are perceived to have high academic expectancy stress in general.

When grouped according to sex, the results revealed that males ($M=2.70$, $SD=0.61$) and females ($M=2.88$, $SD=0.60$) have a high degree of academic expectancy stress; female honor students fared better than their male counterparts. These data imply that females take their studies more seriously than males and try hard to reach the parents' and teachers' expectations. Female honor students anticipate academic challenges to be overwhelming, and they fear they might fail in fulfilling their expectations, resulting in higher academic expectancy stress than their counterparts. It is the nature of female students to be more expressive than male students (Sulaiman et al., 2009). Thus, female students are most likely to report all the discomfort and unpleasant experience perceived during their academic life; on the other hand, male students often resort to denial and tend to keep their thoughts and feelings. Male students also scored high, but they are more withdrawn than females in expressing their fear of failing the expectations towards them because they are easygoing and happy-go-lucky, in general. Supporting these findings with a similar study, Subramani and Venkatachalam (2019) found that females have higher academic expectancy stress than male students.

When classified according to birth order, the results showed that students have a high degree of academic expectancy stress regardless of birth order. Overall, the eldest ($M=2.87$, $SD=0.58$) ranked first, and the last in the list are the youngest (2.8 , $SD=0.68$) honor students. These results may be justifiable since the eldest in the family needs to juggle academic responsibilities, social life, personal commitments, and obligations to their siblings. Knowing their parents' expectations for them to serve as an example to their younger siblings academically contributes a lot to their academic expectancy stress. The middle and only children also scored high, indicating that they likewise experience mental discomfort and often doubt their abilities due to high academic expectancy stress.

On the other hand, those who are the youngest children scored the lowest, although they similarly have a high degree of academic expectancy stress. These findings reinforce the other studies' findings that regardless of birth order, students experience high academic expectancy stress from personal expectations to excel and the thoughts of failing to live up to their academic expectations. In line with these findings, Reyes-Baybay (2018) claims that older siblings serve as an intellectual resource to their younger siblings, which contributes to their high academic expectancy stress, as the present study reveals that the eldest students obtained better results, among others.

Regarding the strand, students enrolled in TVL-HES ($M=2.95$, $SD=0.44$) scored highest among other strands, and ABM ($M=2.74$, $SD=0.64$) got the lowest score. Nevertheless, all strands got a high degree of academic expectancy stress. It means that students enrolled in non-science programs have high academic expectancy stress, most likely because they want to prove that they can also excel. They experience a tremendous amount of academic expectancy stress as they try to prove that they are not inferior. On the other hand, it is essential to note the common notion that those enrolled in science and technology are held supreme among the programs. Thus, students enrolled in science and technology-related strand experience lower academic expectancy stress compared to those in the other programs.

The honor students with gold ($M=2.80$, $SD=0.64$) and silver ($M=2.82$, $SD=0.58$) distinctions obtained a high degree of academic expectancy stress with a very minimal difference in mean scores.

There was a slight difference in their mean score, indicating that both gold and silver academic honor students greatly suffer from high academic expectancy stress. This result also implies that the student's attitudes towards their academics are developed based on their assessment of their beliefs and expectations. Furthermore, it signifies that the higher your academic award is, the lower the academic expectancy stress. Since they already possess the highest academic honors, they experience minimal academic expectancy stress. Nevertheless, those who are just next to the highest award experience higher academic expectancy stress because they feel that they have failed to live up to their expectations and that they are not good enough, which often leads to higher academic expectancy stress. The results of this study are similar to Arevalo et al. (2018), which stated that students with high educational attainment, whether academic, non-academic, or external, have similar academic expectancy stress levels.

Table 2. Degree of Academic Expectancy Stress

Variables	M	SD	Interpretation
Sex			
Male	2.70	0.61	High
Female	2.88	0.60	High
Birth Order			
Eldest	2.87	0.58	High
Middle	2.8	0.68	High
Youngest	2.76	0.62	High
Only Child	2.81	0.51	High
Strand			
STEM	2.79	0.62	High
ABM	2.74	0.64	High
HUMSS	2.91	0.54	High
TVL-HES	2.95	0.44	High
Academic Honor			
Gold	2.80	0.64	High
Silver	2.82	0.58	High
Family Monthly Income			
Low	2.83	0.64	High
Average	2.8	0.61	High
High	2.75	0.56	High
<i>As a whole</i>	<i>2.81</i>	<i>0.61</i>	<i>High</i>

In terms of their monthly family income, results revealed that students with below-average family monthly income ($M=2.83$, $SD=0.64$) acquired the highest mean score when compared to their peers from high family monthly income ($M=2.75$, $SD=0.56$). These data show that they all have high academic expectancy stress. These also imply that monthly family income dramatically affects the degree of students' academic expectancy stress in terms of the students' need to achieve their personal and parental expectations. Also, students belonging to a family with a low monthly income have a higher degree of mental distress regarding anticipated academic frustrations and not living up to their family's expectations. High academic expectancy stress is also associated with limited resources and inadequate study facilities due to lower monthly family income. They are more susceptible to higher academic expectancy stress that eventually leads to burnout if not controlled. The results align with Sonali's (2016) findings that lower socioeconomic status is directly associated with higher academic stress.

According to Subramani and Venkatachalam (2019), the quality of students in society is based on their academic performance, thus, making academics a great source of stress. Generally, parents expect their children to perform well in academics to prove their social status. Moreover, teachers and the school have high expectations for their students to uphold the institution's reputation and prestige. These expectations from parents, family, peers and teachers contribute significantly to the high degree of academic expectancy stress of senior high school honor students. In other words, senior high school honor students experienced high academic expectancy stress because of the expectations imposed by their parents. Aside from the parents, the senior high school honor students are expected to maintain

and comply with the department's standards for quality assurance. They are sent to a private Catholic School that likewise imposes enormously high education standards.

Based on the expectancy-value theory, students' attitudes are developed and modified based on their assessment of their beliefs and values. Students experience high academic expectancy stress because they desire to achieve academic honor. Another factor that affects their academic expectancy stress is their fear of failing and not reaching their academic expectations. Thus, failing their needs to acquire gratification and a sense of fulfillment to achieve an expectation dramatically contributes to their academic expectancy stress.

Degree of Mental Toughness. Table 3 presents the degree of mental toughness of senior high school honor students in a Catholic school in Negros Occidental. As a whole ($M=2.86$, $SD=0.33$), there is a high degree of mental toughness among senior high school honor students. As a whole ($M=2.86$, $SD=0.33$), there is a high degree of mental toughness among senior high school honor students. This signifies that honor students have a high mental ability to resist, manage and overcome doubts, worries, concerns, and circumstances that obviate success. Concerning the sex of the senior high school honor students, females ($M=2.89$, $SD=0.31$) surpassed male students ($M=2.82$, $SD=0.35$). When grouped according to birth order, the eldest obtained 2.88 ($SD=0.29$), while the youngest garnered a mean score of 2.83 ($SD=0.39$). With regards to their strand, students from HUMSS ($M=2.93$, $SD=0.32$) ranked first, while TVL-HES ($M=2.83$, $SD=0.42$) ranked last in the list. Concerning the academic honors of the senior high school students, those who garnered gold distinction acquired 2.88 ($SD=0.31$), and silver distinction scored 2.83 ($SD=0.35$). When grouped according to monthly family income, senior high school honor students belonging to the family with low monthly income ($M=2.88$, $SD=0.37$) got the highest mean score compared to students belonging to families with average monthly income ($M=2.83$, $SD=0.31$).

When taken as a whole, senior high school honor students scored high with a mean score of 2.86 ($SD=0.33$), meaning they have high mental toughness. A high degree of mental toughness is interpreted to be a high degree of mental ability to resist, manage, and overcome doubts, worries, and circumstances that obviate honor students'. These data indicate that despite the emerging difficulties, honor students are committed to pursuing their goals, perceive the situation as an opportunity to develop, and believe that failure and setbacks are worthwhile experiences that fuel them to move towards their aspirations in life continually.

Moreover, an individual with a high degree of mental toughness can tolerate enormous academic, personal, or life-related stress. They can turn the negative impact of stress into productive and flourishing results. They are fully aware that their mindset is the key to successfully achieving their academic and personal goals despite the overwhelming circumstances they may face along their journey. The study results are similar to Endozo (2019) claim that a high level of mental toughness is associated with coping with pressure among university students, which can be justified by the high degree of mental toughness among senior high school honor students.

Regarding the sex of the senior high school honor students, the results revealed that both males ($M=2.82$, $SD=0.35$) and females ($M=2.89$, $SD=0.31$) obtained a high degree of mental toughness, but females had better results compared to males students. The implication is that female students thrive even when immersed in a very competitive environment (McDonough & Walters, 2001). It is believed that females must prove that being feminine does not mean being more vulnerable than their counterparts (Parker, 2018). This justification explains why females need to be mentally tough in order to overcome judgment and criticism. Contrarily, males tend to suppress their emotions in order for them to prove that they are tough (Zakrzewski, 2014), thus, paving the way for the development of their mental toughness. They tend to protect their image to avoid being judged in a society where social norms dictate that males often symbolize masculinity (Clemens, 2017). In this context, they need to be emotionally tough to avoid being vulnerable to criticism. This significant concern needs a high mental ability to resist and manage doubts despite their vulnerabilities.

This study's findings differ from the findings of Matud (2004), which claim that males are better in terms of their coping mechanisms than females, who often suffer and report chronic stress due to poor mental toughness. These findings strongly suggest that females effectively equate their overwhelming academic demands, which allows them to perceive stress as non-threatening, thereby contributing to developing their high mental toughness.

When grouped according to birth order, results showed that honor students have a high degree of mental toughness regardless of birth order, but the eldest ($M=2.88$, $SD=0.29$) have better results than the youngest ($M=2.83$, $SD=0.39$). These suggest that eldest children are given autonomy and responsibility by their parents to manage their worries and doubts (Wray-Lake et al., 2010), allowing them to develop their mental toughness. A responsibility allows a person to control and be accountable

because whatever happens is their sole responsibility (Whiteman et al., 2003). Accordingly, it provides an avenue for an individual to develop mental toughness.

Table 3. Degree of Mental Toughness

Variables	M	SD	Interpretation
Sex			
Male	2.82	0.35	High
Female	2.89	0.31	High
Birth Order			
Eldest	2.88	0.29	High
Middle	2.87	0.29	High
Youngest	2.83	0.38	High
Only Child	2.87	0.29	High
Strand			
STEM	2.84	0.32	High
ABM	2.87	0.35	High
HUMSS	2.93	0.32	High
TVL-HES	2.83	0.42	High
Academic Honor			
Gold	2.88	0.31	High
Silver	2.83	0.35	High
Family Monthly Income			
Low	2.88	0.37	High
Average	2.83	0.31	High
High	2.86	0.28	High
As a whole	2.86	0.33	High

Students belonging to the youngest category scored the lowest among the group. This result may signify that later-born children have a lower degree of mental toughness than any other category because they lack being pampered and protected by their parents; given the fact that they are the youngest among siblings, they receive more attention and are required to merely follow their elder siblings that hinder the development of their mental toughness. The results of the current study are similar to the findings of Easey et al. (2019), which stated that later-born children are more susceptible to mental health problems because of poor coping mechanisms, which is justified by the results of this study.

When classified according to the strand, the results revealed that whatever the strand of honor students have a high degree of mental toughness, HUMSS (M=2.93, SD=0.32) garnered the highest mean score, and TVL-HES (M=2.83, SD=0.42) got the lowest mean score. These imply that honor students are well-versed in stress optimization and dare to conquer their fears and limitations despite the unfavorable environment of pressurized situations. Honor students from STEM garnered the lowest mean score in terms of mental toughness.

Moreover, STEM is an introductory level for students who wish to pursue a medical and engineering course, which means that STEM honor students have a potential risk of being inconsistent. Also, they may lose control over stressful situations compared to honor students pursuing HUMSS that strive to achieve balance and equate the demands brought by a pressurized situation, subsequently allowing them to better cope with the situation (Pacheco, 2008). In connection with this, the present study is in line with the findings of Naveen et al. (2015), which concluded that students enrolled in medical-related courses have a high level of stress because of poor coping strategies, which is justified by the better results of the students pursuing HUMSS compared to those under the STEM strand. These findings confirm that poor coping mechanisms cause lower mental toughness.

In terms of their academic honors, results showed that students with gold ($M=2.88$, $SD=0.31$) and silver ($M=2.83$, $SD=0.35$) academic honors obtained a high degree of mental toughness. However, students with gold academic honors fared better than their silver academic honor counterparts. This result implies that those with high academic honors perceived they could handle their problems and control stressful situations (Aguilar-Vafaie & Abiari, 2007). They have a clear sense of purpose and are motivated to achieve their goals. Furthermore, the result signifies that regardless of academic honor, senior high school students consistently achieve and perform despite the competitive environment (Gustems et al., 2019). They are not insecure and see the challenges as opportunities to grow. They are focused on whatever goals they set, understand that coping is a critical variable in managing stress, and persevere to achieve them despite the challenging situations they may encounter (Gustems & Calderon, 2013). In the same line, Aguilar-Vafaie and Abigail (2007) stated that students with lower academic performance perceived their problems as out of control. This statement is relevant to the result of this study, which shows that students with gold academic honors have higher mental toughness than those with silver academic honors.

The difference in the Degree of Academic Expectancy Stress. An Independent sample t-test was used to determine the significant difference in the degree of academic expectancy stress when the senior students are classified by sex and academic honors, as illustrated in table 4. The difference was significant in terms of sex in the academic expectancy stress ($p=0.027$), with the male students ($M=2.70$) significantly lower than the female students ($M=2.88$). In terms of academic honors, there was no significant difference in academic expectancy ($p = 0.815$), showing that both gold and silver academic honor students have the same degree of academic expectancy stress.

The claims of previous studies (Subramani & Ventakachalam, 2019; Sulaiman et al., 2009; Wood, 2009) are similar to those of the current study regarding the existence of a significant difference between the academic expectancy stress of both sexes. The results of this study differ from the findings of Arevalo et al. (2018), that there is no significant difference between the two genders. These results affirm that female senior high school honor students' academic expectancy stress is notably higher than that of the male senior high school honor students enrolled in a Catholic school in Negros Occidental. These data likewise indicate that female students take academic expectations seriously, contributing to high academic expectancy stress. In contrast, male students take academic stress lightly, contributing to a lower degree of academic expectancy stress than that female students.

The findings of this study signify that female students experience different types of stress compared to male students due to their emotional and sensitive character towards their academics. Having academics as one of the considerations, female students value the importance of dedication towards their schoolwork compared to male students; however, due to their high personal investment into earning an educational experience, they are aware that they will have a lifetime benefit from such dedication (Sulaiman et al., 2009). Furthermore, female students showed more self-regulation compared to boys. Female students tend to abide by rules, pay close attention to specific instructions and be keen on details, and display an overall sense of self-discipline through working through long-term goals despite challenges and failure (Subramani & Venkatachalam, 2019).

This current study shows that there is no significant difference in the degree of academic expectancy stress in terms of academic honors, which is similar to the findings of Arevalo et al. (2018); there is no significant difference in the academic expectancy stress of students with high educational attainment whether they are academic, non-academic, or external scholars. These reveal that although academic expectancy stress affects honor students in general, it does not vary according to the classification of academic honors, making academic honors an insignificant variable to academic expectancy stress.

Table 4. The difference in the Degree of Academic Expectancy Stress when Classified by Sex and Academic Honor

	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Academic Expectancy Stress	2.70 (0.61)	2.88 (0.60)	2.222*	212	0.027
	Academic Honor		t	df	p-value
	Gold	Silver			
	2.80 (0.64)	2.82 (0.58)	0.234	212	0.815

Table 5 shows that the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that the difference was not significant when grouped according to the strand ($p = 0.642$), birth order ($p = 0.750$), and family monthly income ($p = 0.747$).

These results reveal that the number of strands, birth order, and family monthly income is insignificant variables appertaining to the degree of academic expectancy stress of senior high school honor students.

High academic expectancy stress among HUMSS, STEM, and ABM students is similar to the findings of Arevalo et al. (2018) that students enrolled in Psychology, Medical Technology, and Entrepreneurship have high academic expectancy stress, which are courses in line with the strands of the senior high school curriculum. In the same study, Arevalo et al. (2018) concluded that the course is not a significant variable directly connected with student scholars' academic expectancy stress. This conclusion is in line with the results of this study, which show that students are likely to experience academic expectancy stress, whatever strand they belong to.

Table 5. The difference in the Degree of Academic Expectancy Stress when Classified by Strand, Birth Order, and Monthly Family Income

Variables	Mean Scores				F	p-value
Strand	STEM	ABM	HUMSS	TVL	0.560	0.642
	2.79	2.74	2.91	2.95		
Birth Order	Eldest	Middle	Youngest	Only Child	0.404	0.750
	2.87	2.80	2.76	2.81		
Family Monthly Income	Low	Average	High		0.292	0.747
	2.83	2.80	2.75			

The study findings are also the same as the previous studies, including Khan and Khan's (2013), which found birth order to be an insignificant variable that affects academic stress among medical students. Their study reveals that regardless of birth order, one can experience a relatively high or low degree of academic expectancy stress. The senior high school honors students experience high academic expectancy stress regardless if they belong to the eldest, middle, youngest, or only children group. Birth order is an insignificant variable and does not affect the degree of academic expectancy stress of senior high school honor students.

The results showed no significant difference in the degree of academic expectancy stress among senior high honor students when grouped according to family monthly income. This result is different from the findings of Sonali (2016), which stated that there is a significant difference between the socioeconomic status of students with high and low socioeconomic status. These data suggest that honor students may feel a high degree of academic expectancy stress regardless of their family's monthly income, thus, giving the researcher a ground to refute the previous study's findings.

The difference in the Degree of Mental Toughness. Table 6 shows that an independent sample t-test was used to determine the significant difference in mental toughness when classified by sex and academic honor. The difference was insignificant in the degree of mental toughness in both sex ($p = 0.129$) and academic honors ($p = 0.286$), respectively. The analysis revealed that both male and female students have the same mental toughness, and the same goes for the gold and silver academic honors recipients.

This study's findings showed no significant difference between male and female students regarding their mental toughness. The results are similar to Cabas-Hoyos et al. (2015) findings that both genders did not differ in terms of their coping strategies among university students. These indicate that regardless of their sex, senior high school honor students have a high degree of mental toughness and can cope very well. Both sexes have coping mechanisms contributing to their high degree of mental toughness, implying that sex is an insignificant variable to consider when exploring the degree of mental toughness.

The results show no significant difference in the degree of the mental toughness of senior high school honor students when classified according to academic honor, is the findings of Aguilar-Vafaie and Abiari (2007). They stated that high-achieving students considered that stressful situations were

within their control. This further confirms that high achieving students, such as honor students, actively cope with their stress and have control over stressful situations; thus, these contribute to their high degree of mental toughness. Moreover, this means that academic honor is not a significant variable when studying the mental toughness of senior high school honor students.

Table 6. The difference in the Degree of Mental Toughness when Classified by Sex and Academic Honor

	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
Mental Toughness	2.82 (0.35)	2.89 (0.31)	1.523	212	0.129
	Academic Honor		t	df	p-value
	Gold	Silver			
	2.88 (0.31)	2.83 (0.35)	1.071	212	0.286

Table 7 contains the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant difference in the degree of mental toughness when classified by strand, birth order, and monthly family income. The difference was not significant when classified according to the strand ($p = 0.614$), birth order ($p = 0.874$), and monthly family income ($p = 0.620$).

The findings of Naveen et al. (2015) were in line with the results of the present study, which showed that there is no significant difference among the courses of college students, supporting this study, where the strand of senior high school students was found insignificant to their degree of mental toughness. On the other hand, a study conducted by Shiva Kumar et al. (2018) found a significant difference in students' courses, which means that regardless of the students' strand, they can have either a high or low degree of mental toughness.

Riordan et al. (2012) concluded that only children had been previously shown to have a higher risk of self-harm due to poor coping mechanisms. The findings of the current study differ from the previous studies' claims because there is no significant difference in the degree of the mental toughness of senior high school honor students when grouped according to their birth order. It is suggested that regardless of their birth order, the degree of the mental toughness of honor students will remain the same.

Concerning socioeconomic status, studies have concluded that socioeconomic status is a significant variable that categorizes the difference in mental toughness among students belonging to families with higher socioeconomic status and lower socioeconomic status (Elgar et al., 2015; Reiss, 2013; Senn et al., 2014; Weyers et al., 2010;). These studies differ from the current study revealing the non-significant difference in the degree of the mental toughness of senior high school honor students when classified according to family monthly income. Data suggest that the students belonging to families with low, average, or high family monthly income will have no variation in the degree of mental toughness among senior high school honor students.

Table 7. The difference in the degree of Mental toughness when Classified by Strand, Birth Order, and Monthly Family Income

Variables	Mean Scores				F	p-value
Strand	STEM	ABM	HUMSS	TVL	0.560	0.642
	2.84a	2.87a	2.93a	2.83a		
Birth Order	Eldest	Middle	Youngest	Only Child	0.404	0.750
	2.88a	2.87a	2.83a	2.87a		
Family Monthly Income	Low	Average	High		0.292	0.747
	2.88a	2.83a	2.86a			

Relationship between Academic Expectancy Stress and Mental Toughness. Table 8 shows the statistical analysis results using Pearson correlation (r) to determine the significant relationship between academic expectancy and mental toughness. There was a weak positive linear correlation between academic expectancy stress and mental toughness ($r = 0.395$). The relationship was significant at $p = 0.000$, which means enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between academic expectancy and mental toughness. The higher the degree of academic expectancy stress among honor students, the better their mental ability. This analysis implies that the higher the mental distress, the higher the mental toughness. It further signifies that academic expectancy stress is linked with mental toughness, validated by the study (Kotter et al., 2017).

Ross and Mirowsky (2006) stated that college students' incidence of mental distress decreases with positive adjustments to their academic expectations. This statement is in line with the results of this study that there is a significant relationship between academic expectancy stress and mental toughness of senior high school honor students in a Catholic School. These data suggest that helping students develop their mental toughness can control their academic expectancy stress, enabling them to perform better in their academics and helping them eliminate academic-related stress. Personality development programs in schools can help increase the mental toughness of honor students and help them cope with their academic expectancy stress.

Table 8. Relationship between academic expectancy and mental toughness

Variable		r	df	p
Academic Expectancy Stress Inventory x	Mental Toughness	0.395	212	0.000

Students situate themselves in the world based on their expectations, wherein they try to expect that they will become honor students; thus, it forms a self-fulfilling prophecy that allows them to meet their expectations (Arevalo et al., 2018). Stressful events such as fear of failure to meet academic expectations help the honor students to cope. This fuels the honor students' desire to equate and balance the demands brought by the pressurized situation (Pascoe et al., 2019).

The findings of this study suggest that honor students develop and modify their attitudes based on assessments of beliefs and values. They accentuate the importance of outcome expectations in making behavioral decisions. Honor students have a high degree of academic expectancy stress. However, the students assessed these expectations and contributed to their behavioral decisions in satisfying their need for gratification and a sense of fulfillment toward achieving these expectations.

Additionally, students continuously strive to equate and balance the demands of the pressurized situation to cope with the academic expectancy stress they experience. Academic expectancy stress is believed to be an outcome of the transaction between the senior high school honor students and their complex environment (Lazarus & Folkman, 1987). Furthermore, honor students perceived academic expectancy stress as non-threatening, contributing to developing their mental toughness.

As evidenced by the study's findings, the senior high school honor students experience mental distress concerning anticipated frustration associated with academic failure; however, they possess the mental ability to resist, manage and overcome doubts, worries, concerns, and circumstances that obviates academic success. These signify that when honor students have a high degree of academic expectancy stress, they might also have a high mental toughness. Therefore, the theoretical assumptions of this study were validated.

CONCLUSION

The degree of academic expectancy stress and mental toughness of senior high school honor students enrolled in a Catholic school in Negros Occidental for the academic year 2019 - 2020 was high. Honor students, in general, consider academic expectations to be a great source of stress. These further signify that honor students perceive academic expectations as a positive stress that motivates them to continually achieve and obliterate mental distress concerning their anticipated frustration associated with academic failure. Moreover, honor students possess a mental ability to manage, overcome, and resist concerns, doubts, and circumstances that obviates academic success.

In terms of the difference in academic expectancy stress, female senior high school honor students significantly differed from their male counterparts, making sex the only significant variable. The findings further exhibit the fierce commitment of female students to address their academic expectancy stress compared to their male counterparts. Considering the degree of mental toughness, all variables were found insignificant. The findings generally indicate that students took stress as an

opportunity and challenge to grow and perceived it as non-threatening. There was no significant difference among the variables because Filipinos are generally resilient. Thus, this provides the researcher a ground to reject the first null hypothesis.

Finally, the significant relationship between the academic expectancy stress and mental toughness of senior high school honor students was established; thus, it is appropriate to reject the last hypothesis. Furthermore, honor students' persistent academic expectancy stress and mental toughness can be attributed to the formation and training of a Catholic School that integrates the holistic development of their students. Therefore, although slight variance was found, academic expectancy stress contributes to the mental toughness of senior high school honor students enrolled in a Catholic school.

REFERENCES

- Aguilar-Vafaie, M. E., & Abiari, M. (2007). Coping Response Inventory: Assessing coping among Iranian college students and introductory development of an adapted Iranian Coping Response Inventory (CRI). *Mental Health, Religion and Culture*, 10(5), 489-513.
- Arevalo, Ocoñaola, Pineda, Balinas & Matutino (2018). Pathways to achievement: Expectancies and Academic Success. CRP Riverside College.
- Calaguas, G. M. (2011). The link between academic achievement and academic expectations stress. *Journal of Education and Vocational Research*, 1(3), 106-111.
- Calaguas, G. M. (2012). Parents/teachers and self-expectations as sources of academic stress. *International Journal of Research Studies in Psychology*, 2(1).
- Cabas-Hoyos, C., Espriella, N., German-Ayala, N., Martinez-Burgos, L., & Uribe-Urzola, A. (2015). Coping and gender differences in university students. *European Psychiatry*. 30.1186.
- Drinkwater, K., Dagnall, N., Denovan, A., & Parker, A. (2019). The moderating effect of mental toughness: perception of risk and belief in the paranormal. *Psychological reports*, 122(1), 268-287.
- Easey, K. E., Mars, B., Pearson, R., Heron, J., & Gunnell, D. (2019). Association of birth order with adolescent mental health and suicide attempts: a population-based longitudinal study. *European child & adolescent psychiatry*, 28(8), 1079-1086.
- Elgar, F. J., Pfortner, T. K., Moor, I., De Clercq, B., Stevens, G. W., & Currie, C. (2015). Socioeconomic inequalities in adolescent health 2002–2010: a time-series analysis of 34 countries participating in the Health Behaviour in School-aged Children study. *The Lancet*, 385(9982), 2088-2095.
- Endozo, A. (2019). Structural equation modeling of mental toughness among university learners. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 11(4), 149-149.
- Feld, L. D. (2011). Student stress in high-pressure college preparatory schools.
- Ghosh, S. M. (2016). Academic stress among government and private high school students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 3(2), 119-125.
- Gustems-Carnicer, J., & Calderón, C. (2013). Coping strategies and psychological well-being among teacher education students. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 28(4), 1127-1140.
- Gustems, J., Calderon, C., & Calderón-Garrido, D. (2019). Stress, coping strategies and academic achievement in teacher education students. *European Journal of Teacher Education*. 1-16.
- Juan, M. V. T. (2015). Mental toughness of scholar athletes. *Researchers World*, 6(3), 22.

- Kötter, T., Wagner, J., Brüheim, L., & Voltmer, E. (2017). Perceived medical school stress of undergraduate medical students predicts academic performance: an observational study. *BMC medical education*, 17(1), 1-6.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1987). Transactional theory and research on emotions and coping. *European Journal of personality*, 1(3), 141-169.
- Maghanoy, M.L. (2013). Mental toughness and athletic coping skills in competitive-level Filipino dragon boat paddlers. *University of the Philippines*.
- McDonough, P., & Walters, V. (2001). Gender and health: reassessing patterns and explanations. *Social science & medicine*, 52(4), 547-559.
- Matud, M. P. (2004). Gender differences in stress and coping styles. *Personality and individual differences*, 37(7), 1401-1415.
- Naveen, S., Swapna, M., Jayanthkumar, K., & Manjunatha, S. (2015). Stress, anxiety and depression among students of selected medical and engineering colleges, Bangalore-a comparative study. *Int J Public Ment Health Neurosci*, 2, 14-8.
- Pariat, L., Rynjah, A., Joplin, M., & Kharjana, M. G. (2014). Stress levels of college students: Interrelationship between stressors and coping strategies. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19(8), 40-46.
- Parker, K. (2018). Women in majority-male workplaces report higher rates of gender discrimination.
- Pascoe, M. C., Hetrick, S. E., & Parker, A. G. (2020). The impact of stress on students in secondary school and higher education. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1), 104-112.
- Perino, G.A., Gomez, Q.M., Abecia, M.F., & Moneva, J. (2019). Coping strategies of senior high school graduating students with academic tasks. *International Journal of Science and Research*. 2319-7064.
- Price, R. H., Choi, J. N., & Vinokur, A. D. (2002). Links in the chain of adversity following job loss: how financial strain and loss of personal control lead to depression, impaired functioning, and poor health. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 7(4), 302.
- Reiss, F. (2013). Socioeconomic inequalities and mental health problems in children and adolescents: a systematic review. *Social science & medicine*, 90, 24-31.
- Reyes-Baybay, M. (2018). The relationship of birth order and academic achievement of PUP Santa Rosa Campus second year students. *KnE Social Sciences*, 939-946.
- Riordan, D. V., Morris, C., Hattie, J., & Stark, C. (2012). Family size and perinatal circumstances, as mental health risk factors in a Scottish birth cohort. *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*, 47(6), 975-983.
- Ross, C. E., & Mirowsky, J. (2006). Sex differences in the effect of education on depression: resource multiplication or resource substitution?. *Social science & medicine*, 63(5), 1400-1413.
- Sarita, S. (2015). Academic stress among students: Role and responsibilities of parents. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(10), 385-388.

- Scott, K. M., Von Korff, M., Angermeyer, M. C., Benjet, C., Bruffaerts, R., De Girolamo, G., & Kessler, R. C. (2011). Association of childhood adversities and early-onset mental disorders with adult-onset chronic physical conditions. *Archives of general psychiatry*, 68(8), 838-844.
- Senn, T. E., Walsh, J. L., & Carey, M. P. (2014). The mediating roles of perceived stress and health behaviors in the relation between objective, subjective, and neighborhood socioeconomic status and perceived health. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, 48(2), 215-224.
- Sonali, S. (2016). Role of socioeconomic status in academic stress of senior secondary students. *Int J Adv Educ Res*, 12, 44-50.
- Springer, K. W., Sheridan, J., Kuo, D., & Carnes, M. (2007). Long-term physical and mental health consequences of childhood physical abuse: Results from a large population-based sample of men and women. *Child abuse & neglect*, 31(5), 517-530.
- Subramani, C., & Venkatachalam, J. (2019). Parental expectations and its relation to academic stress among school students. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 6(2), 95-99.
- Sulaiman, T., Hassan, A., Sapian, V. M., & Abdullah, S. K. (2009). The level of stress among students in urban and rural secondary schools in Malaysia. *European journal of social sciences*, 10(2), 179-184.
- Weyers, S., Dragano, N., Möbus, S., Beck, E. M., Stang, A., Möhlenkamp, S., ... & Siegrist, J. (2010). Poor social relations and adverse health behavior: stronger associations in low socioeconomic groups?. *International Journal of Public Health*, 55(1), 17-23.
- Whiteman, S. D., McHale, S. M., & Crouter, A. C. (2003). What parents learn from experience: The first child as a first draft?. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 65(3), 608-621.
- Wray-Lake, L., Crouter, A. C., & McHale, S. M. (2010). Developmental patterns in decision-making autonomy across middle childhood and adolescence: European American parents' perspectives. *Child development*, 81(2), 636-651.
- Zakrzewski, V. (2014). Debunking the Myths about Boys and Emotions. *Greater Good*. <https://greatergood.berkeley.edu>

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.